

Antidiabetic Effects of Thymol and Beta Carophylene Compounds from *Ocimum gratissimum* Linn Using *in silico* and *in vivo* Approaches

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Abstract

Ocimum gratissimum (OG) Linn. is known to possess hypoglycemic activities, and its phytochemicals, which include thymol and beta-carophylene (BCP), have also been reported to demonstrate hypoglycemic activity. Therefore, this study investigated the antidiabetic activity of thymol and BCP using *in vivo* and *in silico* approaches. Twenty male Wistar rats were divided into four groups (n=5): Control, DIA, DIA+THY, and DIA+BCP for the *in vivo* study. The control group comprised normal animals; while diabetes mellitus was induced in the DIA, DIA+THY, and DIA+BCP groups by alloxan monohydrate (100 mg/kg, i.p), followed by oral administration of distilled water, thymol (20 mg/kg), and BCP (200 mg/kg) respectively, for 14 days. Fasting blood glucose (FBG), hepatic glucose-6-phosphatase activity, and liver functions were determined. *In silico*, thymol and BCP were docked with peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (PPAR- α), peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR- γ), insulin receptor (IR), protein tyrosine phosphatase 1B (PTP1 β), dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4), glycogen synthase kinase-3 β (GSK-3 β), and aldose reductase (AR) using the AutoDock Vina plugin in PyRx software. Additionally, the absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) profile of thymol and BCP were determined. Elevated FBG and hepatic glucose-6-phosphatase activity were observed in the DIA group, and these were significantly reduced by thymol and BCP treatment in the DIA+THY and DIA+BCP groups, respectively. All the targeted proteins docked favourably with either thymol or BCP however, the least binding affinities were observed in AR and DPP-4. Both thymol and BCP had ADMET scores that met the decision rule for toxicity and safety. We concluded that thymol and BCP inhibit glucose-6-phosphatase activities in diabetic rats and may likely modulate aldose reductase and DPP-4 activity to bring about their antidiabetic properties, among other favorable pathways.

Keywords: Thymol, Beta-Carophylene, Glucose-6-phosphatase, Aldose reductase, dipeptidyl peptidase-4

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a derailment in glucose homeostasis occasioned by hormonal insufficiency or insensitivity of peripheral tissues to hormonal action (Kotas and Medzhitov, 2015). It is a major public health concern, with 537 million people living with diabetes worldwide (Sun *et al.*, 2022). In 2021, it was the direct cause of 1.6 million human deaths, 47 % of which occurred before the age of 70 years (WHO, 2024). The current projection for diabetes incidence in 2030 is 643 million, expected to rise to 783 million by 2045, with the majority occurring in middle- and low-income countries (Sun *et al.*, 2022) where substantial costs are currently incurred in the management of diabetes (Moucheraud *et al.*, 2019). As of 2021, 3.6 million out of 96.8 million adult Nigerians were diabetic, translating to a prevalence rate of 3.7% (IDF, 2024), despite the high proportion being undiagnosed (WHO, 2016). The search for diabetes cures from medicinal plants, which are ubiquitously available in the country, is vigorously ongoing (Oridupa and Saba, 2018). Relatively low cost, accessibility, and the perception of being natural are strong motivators for seeking alternatives to conventional healthcare in Sub-Saharan African countries (James *et al.*, 2018).

Ocimum gratissimum (OG) Linn leaf known in Nigeria as *efirin*, *Nehonwu*, and *ai daya ta guda* by the Yoruba, Igbo, and Hausa, respectively, is documented to have hypoglycemic activities (Aguiyi *et al.*, 2000; Owoyele *et al.*, 2005; Onalapo *et al.*, 2011; Oguanobi *et al.*, 2012; Casanova *et al.*, 2014; Shittu *et al.*, 2016; Okoduwa *et al.*, 2017). *Ocimum gratissimum* inhibited hepatic glycogen phosphorylase activity in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats (Shittu *et al.*, 2018), reversed diabetes-induced intestinal hyperplasia in alloxan diabetic rats (Shittu *et al.*, 2019a), and enhanced insulin sensitivity in rats with metabolic syndrome (Shittu *et al.*, 2021). Despite these promising antidiabetic activities, crude extract of OG may precipitate infertility in diabetic rats (Shittu *et al.*, 2019b), thus calling for the need to identify the exact antidiabetic component(s).

Using GC-MS analysis, we identified 12 bioactive components in OG; among these identified components, thymol had the highest concentration, and we recently documented its

amelioration of diabetes-induced exocrine pancreas insufficiency (Shittu *et al.*, 2024) in addition to the numerous reports on its hypoglycemic activity (Saravanan and Pari, 2015). Another component of OG with proven hypoglycemic activity is beta-carophyllene (BCP) (Mani *et al.*, 2021; 2022). Therefore, we further investigated the antidiabetic activities of these two bioactive components of OG by exploring their drug-likeness activity, molecular docking (*in silico*), and effects on glucose-6-phosphatase activity in alloxan-induced diabetic male Wistar rat (*in vivo*).

Materials and Methods

In silico Experiment

Collection of Ligands and Selected Target Proteins

The selected ligands were two phytochemicals from *Ocimum gratissimum* leaf extract, namely thymol and BCP. The two ligands were downloaded from PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) by providing their names on the search function. The 3D SDF format of the two phytochemicals were downloaded for further studies.

The PDB format of the selected target proteins were searched on Protein Databank and downloaded with the following PDB IDs: Insulin receptor (IR) (PDB ID: 4XST), protein tyrosine phosphatase 1B (PTP1 β) (PDB ID: 1G7F), dipeptidyl peptidase (DPP)-4 (PDB ID: 2RGU), glycogen synthase kinase-3 β (GSK-3 β) (PDB ID: 6Y9S), and aldose reductase (AR)(PDB ID: 4LBS), with the exception of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (PPAR- α), and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR- γ), which were not available on the database. Hence, the predicted model of the proteins PPAR- α and PPAR- γ were downloaded from AlphaFold Protein Structure Database (<https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk/>), developed by DeepMind and EMBL-EBI, having model numbers AF-Q07869-F1 and AF-P37231-F1, respectively.

Preparation of Selected Protein Targets

The five proteins, IR, DPP-4, GSK-3 β , AR and PTP1 β , downloaded from Protein Databank were prepared using BIOVIA discovery studio to remove the existing ligands, heteroatoms, and

water molecules. Afterwards, the Chimera 1.1.4 software (Dock Prep Plugin built-in) was used to add hydrogen bonds and gasteiger charges to all the seven proteins to avoid docking interference (Afolayan *et al.*, 2024).

Molecular Docking Simulation

Simulated dockings were performed between the two phytocompounds of interest, namely thymol and BCP, and selected target proteins, including PPAR- α , PPAR- γ , IR, PTP1 β , DPP-4, GSK-3 β , and AR. These were done by using Auto Dock Vina plugin in PyRx software to load the molecules and the ligands (phytocompounds). After completing the docking process, the binding affinity scores were downloaded in an Excel sheet, while Discovery Studio 2021 was used to visualize the 2D representation of each ligand-protein complex (Afolayan and Tarkaa, 2023).

Druglikeness and Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity (ADMET) Profile

The drugability of the two ligands were tested based on the Lipinski's rule of five. This rule states that drug is likely to have poor permeation and poor absorption if it violates more than one of the followings: The molecular weight should not be more than 500; Log P should not be more than 5; number of hydrogen bond donors should not be more than 5; and lastly, the number of hydrogen bond acceptors should not be more than 10 (Pollastri, 2010). The four parameters, namely molecular weight, Log P, number of hydrogen bond donors, and number of hydrogen bond acceptors, were determined by using the SwissAdme database (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>).

Further, the ADMET profile of the phytocompounds were predicted to assess pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic parameters, such as gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, blood brain barrier (BBB) permeant, P-glycoprotein (Pgp) substrate, inhibition of cytochrome P variants, oral bioavailability, and toxicity. Aside from the toxicity class, all the parameters were predicted by submitting the canonical smiles of each phytocompound to the SwissAdme database. Additionally, the canonical smiles of the phytocompounds, which were obtained from the PubChem database, were submitted on Prottox II server ([\[new.charite.de/prottox_II/index.php?site=compound_input\]\(https://tox-new.charite.de/prottox_II/index.php?site=compound_input\)\) to predict the toxicity class that ranged from 1 to 6, with the lowest score being fatal and the highest being non-toxic.](https://tox-</p>
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In vivo Experiment

Animals

Twenty male Wistar rats (200 \pm 40 g) were used for the study. The animals were kept in well-aerated plastic cages covered with wire mesh in the animal house of the Department of Physiology, College of Medicine, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. They were kept under ambient temperature of 25 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C, humidity of 46%, and light/dark cycle of 12/12h. They were given standard pelletized rat feed (Ladokun feeds $^{\circ}$, Composition: 26.5% protein, 40% carbohydrate, 29%Fat, and 4.5%crudefibre) and water, *ad libitum*. Acclimatization was done for 2 weeks prior to the commencement of the study. All experimental protocols and handling were in compliance with the University of Ibadan Ethical code on animal use and handling for experiment (Approval number: UI-ACUREC/075-0524/21).

Preparation of thymol and BCP for administration

The thymol solution was prepared by dissolving thymol (BDH Chemicals Ltd., Poole, England) in 0.5% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). It was stirred gently over boiling water to facilitate easy dissolution. After it was completely dissolved, the solution was transferred to a sterile amber glass bottle for storage in the refrigerator, from which it was dispensed daily for oral administration. 0.901 g/mL BCP stock (Sigma $^{\circ}$, St. Louis) was reconstituted in corn flour oil to achieve a 200 mg/mL solution and stored in an amber bottle.

Induction of diabetes

Diabetes mellitus was induced in the rats by intraperitoneal administration of 100mg/kg body weight of alloxan monohydrate (Sigma, St. Louis, USA) following an overnight fast. Fasting blood glucose (FBG) was obtained via the tail vein to confirm diabetes after 72 hours of induction using Accu-chek $^{\circ}$ glucometer (Roche Diabetes Care GmbH, Sandhofer Strasse 116 68305, Mannheim,

Germany). Rats with FBG > 200 mg/dL were included in the diabetic groups.

Experimental Design

After confirming the diabetic status of the rats, the animals were divided into four groups as follows:

- Control: normal rats that were given only distilled water
- DIA: Diabetic rats that were given distilled water
- DIA+THY: Diabetic rats that were given 20mg/kg body weight of thymol (Saravanan and Pari, 2015)
- DIA+BCP: Diabetic rats that were given 200 mg/kg body weight of thymol (Mani *et al.*, 2021)

All administrations were done orally for 14 days, with body weight and fasting blood glucose levels (FBS) monitored weekly. The body weight was measured using laboratory weighing scale while FBS was determined in blood obtained from the tail vein using Accu-chek® glucometer (Roche Diabetes Care GmbH, Sandhofer Strasse 116 68305, Mannheim, Germany).

Sample collection

At the end of the experiment, following an overnight fast, cervical dislocation was carried out, blood was collected by cardiac puncture, and the liver was obtained. The blood was centrifuged at 4000 rpm to collect plasma that was used for the determination of liver function, the liver was rinsed in ice-cold 1.15% KCl, dabbed on filter paper, and placed in phosphate buffer saline (PBS, pH 7.4) for homogenization. The homogenate was centrifuged in a cold centrifuge, and the supernatant was used for the determination of glucose-6-phosphatase activity.

Determination of liver function test

Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine transaminase (ALT) activities were determined in the plasma using commercially available kits (Fortress Diagnostics®, United Kingdom), according to the manufacturer's descriptions. Enzyme activities were expressed as U/L

Determination of Glucose-6-phosphatase activities

Glucose-6-phosphatase activity was determined in the liver using the method of Koide and Oda (1959), as previously described (Shittu *et al.*, 2018). Briefly, 0.3 mL of 0.1 M citrate buffer (pH 6.5), 0.5 mL of 150 mM glucose-6-phosphate solution, and 0.2 mL of liver homogenate were mixed at 37 °C for 1 hour. Thereafter, 1.0 mL of 10% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added to stop the reaction. This was cooled on ice, centrifuged, and the supernatant was obtained to quantify liberated phosphate using ammonium molybdate and ascorbic acid cocktail.

Statistical Analysis

Data obtained were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance and presented as Mean ± Standard error of mean. Statistical significance was determined at $P \leq 0.05$ using Tukey Posthoc test.

Results

Molecular docking analysis

The two phytochemicals docked favourably with all the seven target proteins, including PPAR- α , PPAR- γ , IR, PTP1 β , DPP-4, GSK-3 β , and AR, with no complex having higher than -5.0 binding affinity. AR and DPP-4, in particular, have lesser binding affinities with the ligands compared to other proteins, as shown in Table 1. Thus, the two phytochemicals have stronger interactions with AR and DPP-4.

Among all the protein-ligand complexes, only thymol had hydrogen bond interactions with the amino acid residues of two target proteins, namely DPP-4 and PTP1 β , as shown in Fig. 2A and Fig. 7A, respectively. Meanwhile, only thymol-PPAR- γ complex formed an unfavorable donor-donor interaction (Figure 6), with all other complexes exhibiting van der Waals and hydrophobic interactions, such as alkyl, pi-alkyl, and pi-sigma bonds. The presence of hydrogen bonds and more hydrophobic interactions may favour the stability of the complexes, Figures 1–7.

Table 1. The Binding Affinity Score of the Phytochemicals against Target Proteins

Phytochemicals	PubChem ID	Target Proteins Binding Affinity (Kcal/mol)						
		PPAR- α	PPAR- γ	IR	AR	PTP1- β	DPP-4	GSK-3 β
Thymol	6989	-6.1	-5.7	-5.7	-7.6	-5.2	-6.5	-6.2
Beta-Caryophyllene	5281515	-7.1	-6	-7.1	-8.0	-6	-7.3	-5.9

PPAR- α , peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha; PPAR- γ , peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma; AR, aldose reductase; IR, Insulin receptor; PTP1 β , protein tyrosine phosphatase 1Beta; DPP-4, dipeptidyl peptidase (DPP)-4; GSK-3 β , glycogen synthase kinase-3 β .

Note: The lower the binding affinity score, the more favorable is the interaction.

Figure 1: Two-dimension visualization of the molecular interaction between Insulin Receptor amino acid residues with (A) Thymol and (B) Beta-Caryophyllene

Figure 2: Two-dimension visualization of the molecular interaction between Dipeptidyl peptidase 4 amino acid residues with (A) Thymol and (B) Beta-Caryophyllene.

Figure 3: Two-dimension visualization of the molecular interaction between Aldose reductase amino acid residues with (A) Thymol and (B) Beta-Caryophyllene

Figure 4: Two-dimension visualization of the molecular interaction between Glycogen Synthase Kinase-3β amino acid residues with (A) Thymol and (B) Beta-Caryophyllene

Figure 5: Two-dimension visualization of the molecular interaction between Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor alpha amino acid residues with (A) Thymol and (B) Beta-Caryophyllene

Figure 6: Two-dimension visualization of the molecular interaction between Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor beta amino acid residues with (A) Thymol and (B) Beta-Caryophyllene

Figure 7: Two-dimension visualization of the molecular interaction between Protein tyrosine phosphatase 1 beta amino acid residues with (A) Thymol and (B) Beta-Caryophyllene

Druglikeness and Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity (ADMET) Analysis

None of the two phytochemicals violated any of the rules of Lipinski. However, thymol was predicted to be more soluble compared to BCP, as shown in Table 2. Concerning the ADMET profile of the two phytochemicals, BCP was predicted to have low GI absorption compared to the high GI absorption profile of thymol. Additionally, thymol was predicted to inhibit only one variant of the cytochrome proteins compared to two inhibitions by BCP. However, both were

predicted to be non-substrate of Pgp, relatively safe to swallow, and orally bioavailable in human. Thymol was predicted to be capable of permeating the BBB, contrary to BCP, as shown in Table 3.

Effect of thymol and BCP on Fasting Blood Glucose in alloxan-induced diabetic rats

The effects of thymol and BCP on FBG level are shown in Figure 8. The FBG was significantly elevated in the DIA group (208.60 ± 8.58 mg/dL) when compared with that in the control

Table 2: Physicochemical Properties and Druglikeness of the Phytocompounds

Phytocompound	Formula	MW	#HBA	#HBD	TPSA	iLOGP	Solubility	Lipinski violation
Beta-Caryophyllene	C15H24	204.35	0	0	0	3.29	Moderately	0
Thymol	C10H14O	150.22	1	1	20.23	2.32	Soluble	0

Note: MW, Molecular Weight; #HBA, Number of Hydrogen bond acceptor; #HDA, Number of Hydrogen bond donor; iLogP, Octanol/Water Coefficient. Database used: SwissAdme

Table 3: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, Toxicity parameters of the Phytocompounds

Phytocompound	GI absorption	BBB permeant	Pgp substrate	CYP1A2 inhibitor	CYP2C19 inhibitor	CYP2C9 inhibitor	CYP2D6 inhibitor	CYP3A4 inhibitor	Bioavailability Score	Toxicity Class
Beta-caryophyllene	Low	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	0.55	5
Thymol	High	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	0.55	4

Note: GI, Gastrointestinal; BBB, Blood-Brain Barrier; CYP, Cytochrome.

Toxicity class ranges between 1 and 6, with the most toxic being 1 and the safest being 6.

Database used: SwissAdme and Protox II.

Figure 8: Effect of thymol and beta-carophyllene on fasting blood glucose level of alloxan-induced diabetic male Wistar rats.

mg/dL) when compared with that in the control (83.18 ± 3.31 mg/dL). Treatment with thymol in DIA+THY (125.3 ± 6.53 mg/dL) and BCP in DIA+BCP (128.9 ± 7.63 mg/dl) groups significantly reduced the FBG level when compared with that in the DIA group (208.60 ± 8.58 mg/dL).

Effect of thymol on liver function in alloxan-induced diabetic rats

As shown in table 4, ALT and AST levels were significantly increased in the DIA group (107.2 ± 3.18 U/L and 62.92 ± 1.19 U/L, respectively)

Table 4: Effect of thymol and beta-carophyllene on liver function biomarkers in alloxan-induced diabetic male Wistar rats.

	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)
Control	85.75 ± 1.54	53.79 ± 0.94
Diabetic	107.2 ± 3.18*	62.92 ± 1.19*
DIA+THY	83.84 ± 1.97	50.08 ± 0.64
DIA+BCP	80.87 ± 2.98	51.03 ± 0.66

Note: BCP, beta-caryophyllene; THY, Thymol, ALT, alanine Transaminase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase. *P<0.05

Figure 9: Effect of thymol and beta-carophyllene on hepatic glucose-6-phosphatase activities in alloxan-induced diabetic male Wistar rats.

when compared with the control (85.75 ± 1.54 U/L and 53.79 ± 0.94 U/L, respectively). However, these were significantly (P < 0.05) reduced in DIA+THY (83.84 ± 1.97, 50.08 ± 0.64 U/L, respectively) and DIA+BCP (80.87 ± 2.98, 51.03 ± 0.66 U/L, respectively).

Effect of thymol and BCP on glucose-6-phosphatase activity in alloxan-induced diabetic rats

The effect of thymol on glucose-6-phosphatase activity is shown in Figure 9. Glucose-6-phosphatase activity was significantly (P < 0.05) elevated in the DIA group (19.11 ± 1.37 activity/mg.pr) when compared with that in the

control (10.88 ± 0.60 activity/mg.pr). Treatment with thymol in DIA+THY (12.63 ± 0.59 activity/mg.pr) and BCP in DIA+BCP (10.54 ± 0.57 activity/mg.pr) groups significantly reduced the activity of glucose-6-phosphatase when compared with that in the DIA group (19.11 ± 1.37 activity/mg.pr). There was however no significant difference in the glucose-6-phosphatase activities of the DIA+THY when compared with DIA+BCP.

Discussion

The main objective of this study was to use *in silico* and *in vivo* approaches to investigate the antidiabetic activities of thymol and BCP, which we had earlier identified as components of OG leaf (Shittu *et al.*, 2024), just as documented by several other researchers (Gilles and Antoniotti, 2023; Osarieme *et al.*, 2023; Olorundare *et al.*, 2024). The decreased blood glucose level following treatment of diabetic animals with thymol or BCP in the current study is in line with the well-documented hypoglycemic effect of OG (Aguiyi *et al.*, 2000; Owoyele *et al.*, 2005; Egesie *et al.*, 2006; Mohammed *et al.*, 2007; Onaolapo *et al.*, 2011; Oguanobi *et al.*, 2012; Casanova *et al.*, 2014; Shittu *et al.*, 2016; Okoduwa *et al.*, 2017), as well as thymol (Saravanan and Pari, 2015) and BCP (Mani *et al.*, 2021;2022).

In the current study, decreased blood glucose level occurred with concomitant decrease in the activities of hepatic glucose-6-phosphatase in the thymol or BCP treated alloxan-induced diabetic rats. These effects produced by thymol and BCP were however not significantly different from each other. Glucose-6-phosphatase is the enzyme involved in the final step of two key

glucose releasing pathways, gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis (Westergaard and Madsen, 2001), and its expression in a tissue confers gluconeogenic status upon such tissue. In other words, its expression determines if the tissue will have the ability to homeostatically release glucose into the bloodstream during hypoglycemia; thus, it is abundantly found in gluconeogenic tissues such as the liver, kidney, and small intestine (Mithieux *et al.*, 2006; Shittu *et al.*, 2018; 2020). Its activity is particularly elevated in diabetes mellitus, and suppression of its activity is a therapeutic target in management of diabetes mellitus (Naz *et al.*, 2020). Infact, metformin, a biguanides derivative used as standard drug in diabetes mellitus treatment, targets glucose-6-phosphatase to reduce hepatic glucose production in type 2 diabetes mellitus (Mues *et al.*, 2009; Ota *et al.*, 2009). Accordingly, glucose-6-phosphatase activity, which was hitherto elevated in the diabetic group was inhibited by treatment with either thymol or BCP. These inhibitions were accompanied by reductions in the blood glucose level of the two treated groups.

Molecular docking is a computational technique that predicts the binding affinity of ligands to receptor proteins; it is a formidable tool for drug development that accelerates the identification of molecular targets in the creation of disease-specific new therapies (Agu *et al.*, 2023). While it cannot replace *in vivo* and *in vitro* experimentation, it is a decision-making tool that is handy in drug discovery (Abdolmaleki *et al.*, 2021). In this study, seven target proteins—PPAR- α , PPAR- γ , IR, PTP1 β , DPP4, GSK-3 β , and AR—were docked with either thymol or BCP, and they all docked favorably to form complexes with a binding affinity that was not higher than -5.0 kcal/mol. The rule of thumb in favourable ligand-target protein docking is to be lower than -5.0 (Afolayan *et al.*, 2024), and the highest in the current study was -5.2 kcal/mol, which existed between thymol and PTP1 β . Despite thymol and BCP docking favourably with all the target proteins, the least binding affinities were achieved with AR and DPP-4; thus, they may bear the strongest therapeutic target by thymol or BCP in diabetes mellitus treatment.

Aldose reductase is an aldo-keto reductase enzyme that catalyzes the channeling of glucose into polyol pathway to produce sorbitol, which is

a minor glucose metabolism pathway that occurs *pari passu* with glycolytic pathway during normal glucose homeostasis (Singh *et al.*, 2021). However, in the face of uncontrolled hyperglycemia as occasioned in diabetes mellitus, the excess sorbitol causes free radical generation cum oxidative stress, which is implicated in all complications of diabetes mellitus (Obrosova, 2005; Williamson and Ido, 2012). Therefore, diabetes complications could be effectively prevented by antioxidants, which mop the excessive free radical production (Akpoveso *et al.*, 2023). It is worthy of note that thymol and BCP have been reported *in vivo* to possess high antioxidant capabilities (Gushiken *et al.*, 2022; Abd-Elhakim *et al.*, 2023). These antioxidant capabilities cannot be dissociated from the fact that they are terpenes which are natural antioxidants found in plants (González-Burgos and Gómez-Serranillos, 2012). Thus, the low binding affinity with AR achieved *in silico* in the current study may lend credence to their antioxidant capability *in vivo*. In fact, thymol was documented to directly inhibit AR activity in isolated goat lens with cataract induced by high glucose (Kanchan *et al.*, 2016).

The low binding affinity of thymol and BCP with DPP-4 in the current study is also worthy of note. Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 is an integral protein enzyme found in the membrane of all cells of the body and can be dislodged from cell to circulate as soluble protein in plasma (Deacon, 2019). It cleaves many bioactive substances among which is the hormone glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), which is involved in the homeostatic regulation of normal glucose level through its insulinotropic action (Nathan *et al.*, 1992; Gutniak *et al.*, 1992). High circulating DPP-4 is associated with increased degradation of GLP-1 in diabetes mellitus; thus, DPP-4 inhibitors are being explored in the chemotherapy of diabetes mellitus (Ahrén *et al.*, 2016). Although data on the effect of thymol or BCP on DPP-4 activities are lacking, a recent *in silico* study on secondary metabolites of OG proposed that OG or its metabolites may inhibit DPP-4 activity to bring about its hypoglycemic property (Halayal *et al.*, 2023).

The observed conservation of hepatic function in the thymol and BCP treated diabetic rats in the *in vivo* experiment of the current study matches the safe and non-toxic profiles predicted by the *in*

silico study, based on the two compounds not violating any of the Lipinski rules (Pollastri, 2010) in their ADMET profiles. Other studies have documented similar effects of thymol and BCP in diabetic rats (Saravanan and Pari, 2015; Mani *et al.*, 2021; 2022).

It can therefore be concluded that thymol and BCP inhibit glucose-6-phosphatase activities in diabetic rats and may likely modulate AR and DPP-4 activities to bring about their antidiabetic properties, among other favorable pathways. It is recommended that further *in vivo* studies on the effects of OG, thymol and/or BCP in diabetic animals will throw more light on the *in silico* predictions.

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